

Web3 - The Future of the Internet

Khalid AlFuraih , Abdulkhaliq Albudrees

Abstract:- Web3 is introduced in 2014 to undo all the problems that came about in Web 2.0. This next generation of the internet is focused on shifting power away from big technology companies and towards individual users by Decentralization – instead of relying on a single centralized server, Web3 is built on top of blockchain-powered crypto networks that enable data to be stored across distributed devices worldwide. Ultimately, these distributed nodes can be anything, such as computers, laptops, or even bigger servers. They assist as the framework of the blockchain, collaborating with each other to enable the storage, spread, and safeguarding of data without the need for a trusted third party.

I. INTRODUCTION

An initial overview of what internet was between years 1991-2004 the internet was mostly a punch of static pages meaning that whenever you loaded them they just show some stuff and that was it, some call it read only and there was no logging in or interacting with post - most of early internet was not profitably with Ads it was mostly just like one big Wikipedia or hyperlink together now of course with time there was improvement in things like flash and JavaScript and many different features however during this time the users of the internet were consumers they went to internet to consume information and then WEB 2 started from 2004 till now where the biggest changes was the interactivity of the internet, this meant that not only reading information from the pages but webpages started getting information from us as we viewed Facebook and YouTube and perform google searched the centralized company started collecting data about us so they take it to serve us to stay on their websites longer this made more money for them but eventually they realized they can package up all data they collected on us and sale it to advertisers.

“Web2 is age of targeted advertising and the lack of privacy for its users”

So, Web3 is the next evolution of the internet, probably utilizing blockchain technology in a tool of decentralization, in Web2 you are the product as you are browsing social network but in Web3 some certain of you will be the owner of your data the stuff you post online and this kind of true. There was much debate what to call this new phase of evaluation and some experts would not prefer to name it while other suggested to continue calling it as Web 2 cause still there is no clear definition of Web 2.

II. DECENTRALIZATION IN WEB3

III. WHAT IS DECENTRALIZATION IN WEB3

Web3 will provide privilege to connected data in a decentralized way, different from Web 2.0, which primarily stores data in centralized locations while the Web3 will enable people to interact with each other with data in conjunction with AI and machine learning technology, combining the concept of the Semantic Web. Basically, Web3 will enable decentralized apps to take the place of centralized social networks, although allowing individuals to maintain ownership over their data.

IV. THE BENEFITS OF DECENTRALIZATION

One of the core priceable of WEB 3 would be to slowly undo this structure by creating a decentralized internet this is how Blockchain is powered instead of using a group of servers for the transmission of data Blockchain Technology relies on a PEER-TO-PEER network, a group of devices called nodes collectively store and shared files without any central administration or server, therefore, every node will have equal power and do the same task that means that no singular entity will be able to state control over data, It will be something like a digital democracy each connected device will contribute to the strength of the platform, If peer-to-peer and blockchain technologies sound familiar that's because these are already widely in use today it's the tech that powers crypto currency, a decentralized means of investment in banking that's taken the financial world by storm. Decentralization could fundamentally change how we use the internet, with WEB 3

experts project that we will be freely able to access internet independent of an internet service provider more people will have the ability to control how their assets, data and information are used and monetized online. The internet will be more truly democratic.

V. CONCLUSION

Web 3.0 will be more intelligent with semantic Web technologies connected, open, distributed databases, machine learning, natural language processing, autonomous agents and machine reasoning. And It was important to think through the potential downsides of any new technologies. This includes the technology's limitations, who can access it, and how it can be exploited. But the promise of Web3 is to build new web protocols and infrastructure that will allow developers to build new apps where users bring their own data and where identity is no longer secured to any specific platform to overcome what generally went wrong with Web 2.0, or the current internet as we have it — that many of the apps and the platforms that we use have become very extractive and very exploitative.

REFERENCES

- [1.]What is Web 2.0 - Definition, Advantages and Features (znetlive.com)
- [2.]What is Web 2.0? - Definition from Techopedia
- [3.]Web2 vs Web3 | ethereum.org